

Perceptual Compensation of Reproduction Room Acoustics for Ambisonics Recordings

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Ambisonics is a method for capturing and rendering a sound field accurately if the acoustics of the playback room does not influence the sound field significantly. The acoustics of playback room may, however, cause a noticeable reduction of sound quality. We propose a perceptually-motivated recording and rendering system based on Ambisonics that compensate the reverberation of playback room. In this method, the direct and reverberant sound field components are separated in the spherical harmonics domain which are then spectrally adjusted such that after rendering on the loudspeaker array in the playback room, certain perceptual optimization criteria matched between the recording room and playback room. The perceptual optimization criterion aims for conserving the spectral powers of the direct and reverb sound parts and the Interaural Coherence (IC) of the combined direct and reverb sounds in each auditory band. In contrast to the conventional Ambisonics, only three channels are used for sound rendering of a single source. The subjective ratings of a listening test show a perceptually accurate rendering of the original recorded sound field using the proposed method. In addition, the subjective evaluation showed that this method is robust to the head rotation and small displacements within the reproduction room.

0 INTRODUCTION

A goal of sound playback systems can be capturing of an acoustic scene, for example a performance in a concert hall, and the rendering of that performance in another room in a way that the listeners in the playback room perceive the sound field as very similar. Theoretically, methods such as wave field synthesis (WFS) [1] and Ambisonics [2, 3], make it possible to perfectly reproduce a recorded sound field. In both methods, however, the reproduction room must have boundaries without reflection. In practice, the distortions related to a limited number loudspeakers and the presence of reverberation of the playback room will limit the accurate reproduction of the sound field. Furthermore, most currently available recording microphones support only up to 4th or 5th order Ambisonics. For these orders, the accurate sound-field reconstruction in the high-frequency range is limited to a small area that is called the sweet spot. The large number of loudspeakers required for a good sound-field reproduction at high-frequencies poses a substantial challenge in practical applications.

In the WFS domain, various approaches have been developed to compensate for the effect of the reverberant reproduction room. A method based on WFS theory and plane-wave decomposition is proposed to compensate for

the room reflection in a large area [4]. There are Adaptive wavefield synthesises (AWFS) methods [5] and other similar approaches that regard the dereverberation as an inverse problem that attempts to equalize the transfer function of the playback system in multiple points to minimize the reproduction error in these control positions [6]. This type of multi-point sampling and equalization methods based on inverse filtering may result in poor equalization in the points other than the control positions [7].

In the Ambisonics domain, there are hardware solutions to control the reverb field, for example by using directive loudspeakers to limit the energy of reflections [8]. A two-dimensional room equalization over an extended area using cylindrical harmonics for modelling the room reflections has been proposed in [9]. The drawback of this system is the requirement for a very large amount of equalization filters. Recently a modified version of this method for three-dimensional (3D) space was proposed [10] in which, in contrast to [9], the compensation of the room response is performed in the Ambisonic domain, before the decoding, which results in the reduction of needed correction filters. Beside the efforts to equalize the room response in the Ambisonic domain, the sound intensity that is assumed to be a good predictor of human location perception is used for room compensation in a single sweet spot [11].

This intensity matching approach is also extended to the multizone compensation and reproduction in a reverberant room by defining an intensity-based cost function [12].

Complementary to physically-based WFS and Ambisonics methods, there are perceptually-motivated approaches that do not necessarily reproduce the same sound field, but nevertheless allow for a perceptually accurate reproduction. In the Directional Audio Coding (Dirac) [13], the directional and spatially diffuse parts of a sound are separated using a diffuseness criterion within the time-frequency domain. These parts are then processed and played back in different signal paths. The direct sound, preserving directional cues, is played using Vector Base Amplitude Panning (VBAP) method [14] and the diffuse sound is reproduced by multiple loudspeakers using the decorrelation method to mimic the diffuse sound field. In this approach, the reverberation of the reproduction room is neglected. Also, a modified version of the Dirac using microphone array recordings is proposed that can better handle more than one simultaneous sound source [15].

A method for recording and rendering after perceptually compensation of the reproduction room was proposed in [16]. In this approach, a near-to-source microphone is used to record the direct sound and two distant microphones are used to record the reverb sound. For the reproduction of a processed version of the direct sound, two loudspeakers in front of listener are used. The processed reverb sound is reproduced using two distant dipole loudspeakers oriented such that their directional patterns are predominantly pointing away from the listener in this way predominantly exciting the reverberant field in the reproduction room. In the optimization procedure of this method, energies of direct and reverb sounds are separately compensated in each frequency band by equalization of Room-in-Room impulse responses (RinR_IRs) such that they are matching for a listener in the recording and playback room. The optimization procedure is also including the compensation of Interaural Coherence (IC) [17] between the left and right ear signals to preserve the perceived spatial diffuseness of the sound field in the reproduction room. In order to optimize the required compensation filters, a dummy head is placed in the recording room as the reference and another dummy head in the playback room which is optimized.

Altogether, there are relatively few reports in the literature on compensating the reverberation of playback room. In this study, a perceptually-motivated compensation method in the Ambisonics domain using the main compensation idea of [16] is proposed. But instead of using distributed microphones and loudspeakers, a conventional Ambisonics recording and reproduction setup is used. In this proposed method, the direct and reverb parts are separated after recording and perceptually compensated and reproduced in different signal paths. The paper is organized as follows. In Section 1, the general structure of proposed model is explained. The signal processing formulation in the Ambisonics domain is explained in Section 2. Then in

Section 3, an optimization procedure is provided. In Section 4, the evaluation of algorithm is presented. Finally, a conclusion and future work are presented in Section 5.

1 GENERAL STRUCTURE OF THE PROPOSED METHOD

The general structure of the proposed Ambisonic-based recording and reproduction method is depicted in Figure 1. In the recording room, a rigid spherical microphone array [6] and in the reproduction room, a loudspeaker array is used. The direct part of the recorded sound is extracted using a beamformer created from the recorded spherical harmonics. This beamformed signal and direction of arrival (DOA) information are used for the reproduction of the direct sound. To obtain the reverberant sound field, the spatialized beamformed signal, using the plane-wave model is first subtracted from the encoded Ambisonics channels. Only two Ambisonic channels namely the W channel representing zero order Ambisonics, and the Y channel representing one of 1st order Ambisonic channels with dipole pattern are used to reproduce the reverberant field. Then the resulting direct and reverb signals are processed and filtered using a Gammatone filterbank [18] analyses and synthesis framework. The gain of the Gammatone filter $g_{vibap}^{(i)}$ is used for the energy equalization of direct sound within filter number i . For the reproduction of the reverberant sound field, a mixture of weighted W and Y channels is used. The α^i and β^i gains relating to the Y and W channels, respectively, are used for controlling the Interaural Coherence (IC) within each frequency band corresponding to filter number i . The relative strength of the Y and W component will influence the Interaural Coherence (IC). The overall strength of Y and W channels relates to the overall strength of the reverberant sound component. For the Energy equalization of the reverb sound, another gain $g_{amb}^{(i)}$ is multiplied to α^i and β^i . The gains of Gammatone filters are obtained in an optimization procedure. The binaural room impulse responses (BRIRs) of two dummy heads, one in the recording room as the reference and another in playback room as the target are used in this optimization procedure. This implies that in the optimization, the influence of the reverberation in the reproduction room is compensated in all Gammatone bands. The mathematical details of the signal processing and the optimization are presented in Sections 2 and 3.

Fig.1. The block diagram of the room compensation method. The sound is recorded using a microphone array and is then separated into the direct signal path (red) and reverb signal path (blue). Both the direct and reverb signals are compensated using a Gammatone analysis and synthesis framework before reproduction in the playback room. The direct sound is captured by beamforming and after compensation by gains of the Gammatone filters is reproduced using VBAP. Two Ambisonics channels (W and Y) are used to record the reverb sound and after compensation in Gammatone filters are played back using the conventional Ambisonics. Auditory transfer functions (ATFs) of BRIRs of two dummy heads in the recording and playback rooms are used as the reference and target signals in the optimization procedure to find the gains of the Gammatone filters.

2 RECORDING AND REPRODUCTION

In this section, the signal representation in the Ambisonics domain, the beamforming, and the separation of direct and reverb sounds are presented. In addition, standard Ambisonics reproduction is briefly described.

2.1 Sound Field Representation

The spherical harmonics (SHs) of order n and degree m [19] are defined as:

$$Y_n^m(\theta, \varphi) \equiv \sqrt{\frac{2n+1}{4\pi} \frac{(n-m)!}{(n+m)!}} P_n^m(\cos \theta) e^{im\varphi}, \quad (1)$$

in which, θ and φ are elevation and azimuth angles, respectively, and P_n^m is the associated Legendre polynomial of order n and degree m . The SHs expansion for a point source with amplitude S and wavenumber k located in \mathbf{r}_s is:

$$S \frac{e^{-ik\|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}_s\|}}{\|\mathbf{r}-\mathbf{r}_s\|} = -4\pi i S k \sum_{n=0}^{\infty} \sum_{m=-n}^n h_n^{(2)}(kr_s) j_n(kr) Y_n^m(\theta_s, \varphi_s)^* Y_n^m(\theta, \varphi), \quad (2)$$

where $j_n(kr)$ is the n^{th} order spherical Bessel function of the first kind and $h_n^{(2)}$ is the spherical Hankel function of the second kind. In practice, the order is truncated to a

finite order N . The SHs expansion of the pressure created by a point source propagated in a room is:

$$P(r, \theta, \varphi, k) = \sum_{n=0}^N \sum_{m=-n}^n A_n^m(k) b_n(kr) Y_n^m(\theta, \varphi), \quad (3)$$

where $A_n^m(k)$ are SHs coefficients and $b_n(kr)$ is a parameter that depends on the scattering characteristics of the recording point. This parameter for a rigid spherical microphone array with radius r_e is:

$$b_n(kr) = \begin{cases} j_n(kr) - \frac{j_n'(kr_e)}{h_n^{(2)'}(kr_e)} h_n^{(2)}(kr) & , \text{for rigid sphere} \\ j_n(kr) & , \text{for open sphere} \end{cases} \quad (4)$$

$P(r, \theta, \varphi, k)$ in (3) is assumed to be a summation of the direct and reverberant sounds which can be modeled by plane waves or point source model. The spatial information of the direct sound and all virtual point sources related to the reverb sound are summed in a spherical harmonic coefficient $A_n^m(k)$. The SHs coefficients are obtained by a spherical microphone array:

$$A_n^m(k) = \frac{\sum_{q=1}^Q \alpha_q P(r_e, \theta_q, \varphi_q, k) Y_n^m(\theta_q, \varphi_q)^*}{b_n(kr_e)}, \quad (5)$$

in which, r_e is the radius of microphone array, θ_q and φ_q are respectively the elevation and azimuth angles of microphone positions on the rigid sphere, Q is the number of microphone capsules on the array and α_q are

element weights used because of keeping orthonormality of SHs in order limited discrete approximations [19].

2.2 Direct and reverb sounds capturing

Because of the reverberation in the playback room, it is difficult to control the sound field. Therefore, similar to the DirAC [13], the direct and reverb sounds are recorded and compensated separately before playback as proposed in [16]. For capturing the direct sound, a beamforming is pointed in the direction of the direct sound and is defined in the SH domain. To limit the sidelobe levels in the beamformer, an axis-symmetric beamformer [19] with Dolph-Chebyshev weighting $d_{cheby,n}$ is used (cf. [20]). The beamformer signal is then obtained by:

$$S_{BF}(k, r_a) = \sum_{n=0}^N \sum_{m=-n}^n d_{cheby,n} Y_n^m(\theta_{DOA}, \varphi_{DOA}) A_n^m(k). \quad (6)$$

The direction of arrival (DOA) can be predetermined or estimated. In this paper, we only use the predetermined DOA information. To extract the reverb signal, first the direct sound using DOA information is spatialized:

$$S_{n\ BF}^m(k, r_a) = S_{BF}(k, r_a) \left[Y_n^m(\theta_{DOA}, \varphi_{DOA}) \right]^*. \quad (7)$$

and then is subtracted from the original SHs coefficients:

$$S_{n\ Rev}^m(k, r_a) = A_n^m(k) - S_{n\ BF}^m(k, r_a). \quad (8)$$

In this computation, it is assumed that only one source is active within each time slot.

2.3 Direct and reverb sounds reproduction

The direct sound $S_{BF}(k, r_a)$ is captured by the beamformer in (7). The VBAP technique is used to reproduce the direct sound that is coming from the estimated direction $(\theta_{DOA}, \varphi_{DOA})$ (cf. Eq (6)).

The reference signal $A_n^m(k)$ and reverb signal $S_{n\ Rev}^m(k, r_a)$ are ideally reproduced using the simple source approach presented in [21]. The driving signal of loudspeaker number p for the reference signal is:

$$D_p(k) = -\frac{g_p(k)}{ikR^2} \sum_{n=0}^N \frac{e^{-ikR}}{h_n^{(2)}(kR)} \sum_{m=-n}^n R_n^m(k) Y_n^m(\theta_p, \varphi_p), \quad (9)$$

$$R_n^m(k) = \begin{cases} A_n^m(k) & , \text{reference sound reproduction} \\ S_{n\ Rev}^m(k, r_a) & , \text{reverb sound reproduction} \end{cases}$$

where g_p is a gain for the loudspeaker number p . In this ideal Ambisonics reproduction, it is assumed that the playback room is anechoic. But in practice, the playback room has reverberation that will change quality of the reproduced sound. In addition, there are always non-flat

frequency responses of loudspeakers. For these two main reasons, an equalization is needed to preserve the quality the recorded sound.

3 OPTIMIZATION

3.1 Signals used in the Optimization

Three types of signals are needed for the optimization: 1- reference BRIRs, 2- beamformed direct RinR impulse responses and 3- the reverb RinR impulse responses

For obtaining the reference BRIRs, the recorded SHs are used to be rendered from a virtual loudspeaker array on a dummy head in a simulated ideal anechoic room. The SHs of recorded signal obtained according to Eq (5)

$(H_{n\ rec}^m(k, r_e))$ are used in Eq (9) to construct the driving

signal of each loudspeaker by $A_n^m(k) = H_{n\ rec}^m(k, r_e)$. The driving signal of loudspeaker number p for reference signal is denoted by $D_{ref,p}(k)$ in the frequency domain

and $d_{ref,p}[n] = F^{-1}\{D_{ref,p}(k)\}$ in the time domain, where

$F^{-1}\{\}$ is the inverse Fourier transform operator. The head-related-impulse-response (HRIR) of the left ear reconstructed by P loudspeakers in the simulated anechoic room is:

$$BRIR_{ref,L}[n] = \sum_{p=1}^P d_{ref,p}[n] * hrtf_{p,L}[n]. \quad (10)$$

The derivation of the right ear signal is identical only L is replaced by R superscripts. $BRIR_{ref,L}$ and $BRIR_{ref,R}$ are used as the reference signals for optimization. From here on, the formulation is only written for the left ear.

To obtain the beamformed direct RinR impulse responses, the beamformed RIR (BF) is convolved with BRIRs of the VBAP loudspeakers (SP_1, SP_2, SP_3) to construct the binaural RinR impulse response for the beamformed direct sound ($BRinR_{BF}$) for the left and right ears of a listener in the reproduction room. Eq (5) is used for computation of $H_{BF}(k, r_a)$. In the time domain

this signal is denoted by $h_{BF}[n] = F^{-1}\{S_{BF}(k, r_a)\}$. The beamformed signal reproduced by VBAP [14] in the left ear is:

$$BRinR_{BF,L}[n] = h_{BF}[n] * \sum_{v=1}^3 g_v \times BRIR_{SP_v,L}[n], \quad (11)$$

In which, g_v is the VBAP gain of loudspeakers number v (SP_v).

For a perceptually accurate reproduction, the reverberant sound field is added to the direct sound to create the impression of being in a room. The reverb RinR impulse responses is needed for optimization of the reverb field. Therefore, the remaining non-direct RIR of recording room in the SHs domain is computed by

subtraction of spatialized direct signal from the original SHs signals using Eq (9). Only $W(k) = S_{0\text{Re}v}^0(k, r_a)$ and $Y(k) = S_{1\text{Re}v}^{-1}(k, r_a)$ which are zero order (the pressure) and first order (the pressure derivative along y-axis), Ambisonics respectively, are used here as representations of the reverberant sound field. The Ambisonics coefficients of reverb sound are used to construct the driving signal of loudspeaker p , $1 \leq p \leq P$. The y-axis is assumed to be parallel to the connecting line between both ears of the dummy head in the playback room and this way the combined W and Y channels allow to adjust the Interaural Cross Correlation measured on the listeners ears. The driving signal of one loudspeaker is:

$$\begin{aligned} W_p(k) &= \frac{1}{ik} \frac{e^{-ikR} W(k)}{h_0^{(2)}(kR)} Y_0^0(\theta_l, \varphi_l) \\ Y_p(k) &= \frac{1}{ik} \frac{e^{-ikR} Y(k)}{h_1^{(2)}(kR)} Y_1^{-1}(\theta_l, \varphi_l) \end{aligned} \quad (12)$$

The equivalent time domain signals of Eq (12) are

$$w_p[n] = F^{-1}\{W_p(k)\} \quad \text{and} \quad y_p[n] = F^{-1}\{Y_p(k)\}.$$

The binaural RinR impulse response (*BRinR*) of the reverb sound for the left ear denoted by $BRinR_{\text{Re}v,L}$ is produced by summation of left ear RIRs convolved with $w_p[n]$ and $y_p[n]$ signals:

$$\begin{aligned} BRinR_{\text{Re}v,L}[n] &= \left(\sum_{p=1}^P w_p[n] * h_{p,L}[n] \right) + \left(\sum_{p=1}^P y_p[n] * h_{p,L}[n] \right) \\ &= BRinR_{\text{Re}v,W,L}[n] + BRinR_{\text{Re}v,Y,L}[n]. \end{aligned} \quad (13)$$

3.2 Optimization Procedure

The perceptual parameters used for optimization are the spectral energies of the direct and reverberant parts and the interaural coherence (IC). These optimization parameters were previously used in [16]. By using the optimization procedure, the spectral energies of the direct and the reverb sounds of the reproduced signal should be equal to those of the reference signal. The reference RIR of Eq (11), can be separated to the direct and reverb parts:

$$\begin{aligned} BRIR_{\text{ref},L}[n] &= \\ &BRIR_{\text{ref},\text{dir},L}[n] + BRIR_{\text{ref},\text{rev},L}[n]. \end{aligned} \quad (14)$$

The beamformed direct sound reproduced in the playback room according to Eq (11) can also be separated to the direct and reverb parts:

$$\begin{aligned} BRinR_{BF,L}[n] &= \\ &BRinR_{BF,\text{dir},L}[n] + BRinR_{BF,\text{rev},L}[n]. \end{aligned} \quad (15)$$

The compensation of the spectral energies is performed using a Gammatone analysis and synthesis framework [18] which allows to adjust the ‘Auditory’ Transfer Function (ATF) measured at the dummy heads in the recording and playback rooms to be equal. The gain of Gammatone filter g_{vbap}^i is used for the spectral energy equalization of the direct sound within filter number i . Both of the direct and reverb sounds are filtered by a 4th-order Gammatone filterbank. The Auditory Transfer Function $ATF_{\text{sig}}^{(i)}$ is defined as the energy of a signal at the output of i th filter of Gammatone filterbank. The goal of direct sound equalization is making the spectral energies of beamformed signal reproduced by VBAP in Eq (11) equal to that of direct part of reference signal in Eq (14):

$$ATF_{\text{ref},\text{dir},\text{left}}^{(i)} = \left(g_{\text{vbap},L}^{(i)} \right)^2 ATF_{BF,\text{dir},L}^{(i)}. \quad (16)$$

in which, $g_{\text{vbap},L}^{(i)}$ is the gain of a specific VBAP-driven loudspeaker in each frequency band. A fast-converging method proposed in [22] is used for gain optimization in which the gains overlapping Gammatone filters influence each other. Considering the energy equalization, the negative gains are also avoided in this method. This optimization approach was also used in [16]. The average value of the gains obtained for the left and right ears are used as the final gain of VBAP loudspeakers in each frequency band:

$$g_{\text{vbap}}^{(i)} = \frac{g_{\text{vbap},L}^{(i)} + g_{\text{vbap},R}^{(i)}}{2}. \quad (17)$$

For a plausible reproduction, the reverberation of the recording and playback rooms also needs to be taken into account. For the reproduction of the diffuse sound field only two Ambisonic channels are used; the zero-order Ambisonics (W channel) and one first-order Ambisonic channels with a dipole pattern (Y channel). The Y channel data is used to create an out-of-phase signal in left and right ears of the dummy head that is mixed with the W channel to obtain the desired interaural coherence, at least for the sound field directly travelling from the loudspeakers to the ears of the listener. The interaural coherence will be altered by the reverberation in the playback room, and the combined effect needs to be optimized. This is done by using a weighted summation of W and Y channels, and the gains of these two channels are shown by α^i and β^i , respectively. Energy compensation for the reverb sound is performed by an additional gain $g_{\text{amb}}^{(i)}$ for the W and Y channels. For playback of the compensated reverb sound, all the loudspeakers are used. The direct-sound field component of the recording room is previously subtracted from the W and Y channels. The reproduced reverberant RinR impulse response is including two parts of Eq (13) and the reverb part of Eq (15):

$$\begin{aligned}
BRinR_{Rev,L}^{(i)}[n] &= g_{vbap}^{(i)} BRinR_{BF,rev,L}^{(i)}[n] \\
&+ \alpha^i BRinR_{Rev,W,L}^{(i)}[n] + \beta^i BRinR_{Rev,Y,L}^{(i)}[n] \quad (18) \\
&= g_{vbap}^{(i)} BRinR_{BF,rev,L}^{(i)}[n] + BRinR_{Rev,AMB,L}^{(i)}[n].
\end{aligned}$$

For simplification, the reverb part of Eq (15) are denoted by $BRinR_{Rev,AMB,L}^{(i)}[n]$. The $g_{vbap}^{(i)}$ is the gain of beamformed direct sound that is also multiplied by reverb part of this signal. This signal is included, because the direct and reverb parts of the VBAP loudspeakers are not separable. The α^i and β^i are respectively the gains of the reverb channels Y and W to control the ICs between left and right ear signals in each frequency band. The interaural cross correlation (IACC) and IC are defined as:

$$IACC^{(i)}[q] = \frac{\sum_{m=-\infty}^{m=\infty} BRIR_L^{(i)}[m] BRIR_R^{(i)}[m+q]}{\sqrt{\sum_{m=-\infty}^{m=\infty} (BRIR_L^{(i)}[m])^2} \sqrt{\sum_{m=-\infty}^{m=\infty} (BRIR_R^{(i)}[m])^2}} \quad (19)$$

$$IC^{(i)} = \max(IACC^{(i)})$$

The energy equalization for the reverb signal is separately performed using the $g_{amb,L}^{(i)}$ gain in each frequency band:

$$\begin{aligned}
ATF_{ref,rev,L}^{(i)} &= \\
&\left(g_{vbap}^{(i)}\right)^2 ATF_{BF,rev,L}^{(i)} + \left(g_{amb,L}^{(i)}\right)^2 ATF_{Rev,AMB,L}^{(i)}. \quad (20)
\end{aligned}$$

Similar to the gain averaging of VBAP loudspeakers, the average values of left and right ear gains are considered as the final gain of spherical array loudspeakers in each frequency band:

$$g_{amb}^{(i)} = \frac{g_{amb,L}^{(i)} + g_{amb,R}^{(i)}}{2}. \quad (21)$$

The optimized final signal in each frequency band including direct and reverb sound is:

$$\begin{aligned}
BRIR_{opt,L}^{(i)} &= \\
&g_{vbap}^{(i)} BRIR_{ref,L}^{(i)}[n] + g_{amb}^{(i)} BRinR_{Rev,AMB,L}^{(i)}[n] \quad (22)
\end{aligned}$$

The IC between $BRIR_{opt,L}^{(i)}$ and $BRIR_{opt,R}^{(i)}$ namely IC_{opt}^i is computed and compared with IC_{ref}^i and the absolute error value for each frequency band $IC_{error}^{(i)} = |IC^{(i)} - IC_{ref}^{(i)}|$ is minimized. To find the optimized values of α^i and β^i , a search procedure using equations (18), (19), (20) and (21) is repeated to jointly optimize energy of reverb sound and minimize the $IC_{error}^{(i)}$ of final signal in Eq (22).

Algorithm.1. Calculation of the Optimal Parameters $g_{vbap}^{(i)}$, α^i , β^i and $g_{amb}^{(i)}$.

Step 1: determination the gains of direct sound.

(1) The $g_{vbap}^{(i)}$ are determined according by an iterative algorithm in [22].

Step 2: A grid Searching to jointly find optimal α^i , β^i and $g_{amb}^{(i)}$.

For $-1 \leq \alpha^i \leq 1$ and $-1 \leq \beta^i \leq 1$ with the step size of 0.1 for both α^i and β^i :

(1) The $g_{amb}^{(i)}$ is determined by an iterative algorithm in [22].

(2) Calculate $IC_{error}^{(i)} = |IC^{(i)} - IC_{ref}^{(i)}|$.

Step 3: The α^i , β^i and $g_{amb}^{(i)}$ related to $\min\{IC_{error}^{(i)}\}$ are selected as gains of reverb channels.

This optimization is summarized in Algorithm.1.

4 SIMULATIONS AND EVALUATION OF THE PROPOSED METHOD

4.1 Evaluation by simulated Rooms

In the first evaluation of the proposed method, both of the recording and reproduction rooms are simulated and a listening test was performed. To simulate the recording room, the SMIR toolbox [23] and for simulation of the playback room the RAZR toolbox [24] were used. For both Ambisonics recording and reproduction, a 50-node Lebedev Grid [25] is simulated to encode 4th order Ambisonics incorporating 25 SHs. Two simulated recording scenarios and a playback room are described in Tables 1 and 2, respectively. Considering 44.1 kHz sampling frequency, 42 Gammatone filters are used for analyzing and synthesizing in the proposed approach.

Table 1. Two simulated recording scenarios using the SMIR toolbox [23]. The room dimensions (dim), source position (src pos), microphone position (mic pos) and reverberation time (T60) are given.

	room dim	src pos	mic pos	T60
Scenario 1	(50,20,6)	(6,15,1)	(16,15,1)	750ms
Scenario 2	(50,20,6)	(6,15,1)	(15,10,1)	750ms

Table 2. Simulated loudspeaker array of the playback room by RAZR toolbox [24] with 50-nod Lebedev grid.

room dim	array center	array Radius	T60
(8,5,5)	(2,2,2)	2 m	500ms

The results of optimization for scenario 1 are shown in Figure 2. In panels A and B, the results of energy equalization of reverb sound for left and right ears are depicted and compared with the non-optimized case. Note that for the case that reverberation is not optimized, the reverberant signal extracted according to Eq (18) is simply played back without equalization such as would be done if the playback room was anechoic, leading to an increase of power in the low frequencies. In panels C and D, the ICs of the conventional Ambisonics and optimized signal in comparison to that of the reference signal are shown. Perceptually important frequencies for IC are in frequencies below 1500 Hz in which the auditory system is sensitive to the changes in IC. Only the auditory filters below 1500 Hz are highlighted in the panels C and D. All Gammatone filter bank outputs in this range show a near to ideal compensation of ICs, better than the ICs of conventional Ambisonics without room compensation specifically for the frequency bands near to 1500 Hz. In panels E and F, the ATFs of the optimized signal are compared with that of reference, direct and conventional Ambisonics for the left and right

ears. For comparison, the final RMS values of direct and standard Ambisonics signals are equalized to that of the optimized signal. According to the panels E and F, the playback room has smaller absorption coefficient in the low frequencies for both direct and conventional Ambisonic signals. The direct signal without optimization shows more energy in low frequency, even in comparison to the standard Ambisonics signal. After the optimization, these high-energy components in low frequencies are equalized to that of reference signal. The results of compensation for scenario 2 in which the right ear signal has higher energy are shown in Figure 3. Similar to the scenario 1, there is a good match between the compensated signal and the reference signal in comparison to the non-optimized and conventional Ambisonics for both energy and IC. Specifically for the scenario 2 in comparison to the scenario 1, there are more compensation of ICs in the higher frequencies. The differences between ATFs of optimized signal and that of reference signals in some frequencies in panels A and B are because of averaging in equations (17) and (21).

Fig.2. The results of optimization and comparison with the non-optimized signals for scenario 1. In panels A and B, the ATF of reverb sound at the output of all Gammatone filters for the reference, non-optimized and optimized signals respectively for the right and left ears of dummy head are shown. In panel C and D, the ICs of optimized and conventional Ambisonics and their comparisons with that of reference signal for perceptually important frequencies below 1500 Hz are depicted. After compensation (panel D), there is better matching between ICs of reference and that of the compensated signal in comparison to the conventional Ambisonics (panel C). In panels E and F, the ATF of the reference, direct, optimized and standard Ambisonics signals of scenario 1 for the right and left ears are shown. The optimized signal in comparison to the direct and the conventional Ambisonics is more fitted to the energy curve of the reference signal specifically at the low frequencies that the reverberation is dominant.

Fig.3. The results of optimization and comparison with the non-optimized signals for scenario 2. In panels A and B, the ATF of reverb sound at the output of all Gammatone filters for the reference, non-optimized and optimized signals respectively for the right and left ears of dummy head are shown. In figures C and D, the ICs for perceptually important frequencies below 1500 Hz are depicted. In panels E and F, the ATF of the reference, direct, optimized and standard Ambisonics signals of scenario 2 for the right and left ears are compared.

For subjective evaluation of the proposed method, a multi-stimulus scaling listening test similar to the MUSHRA test [26] was performed. 10 listeners participated in this listening test and rendering scenarios were played over headphones. The rendering scenarios used in this experiment are an ideally reproduced reference signal with Ambisonics (Reference), a reproduced signal in the reverb room using conventional higher-order Ambisonics without room compensation (Amb), only the beamformed direct signal played using VBAP method (Direct), the non-optimized signal consisting of direct signal produced by VBAP loudspeaker plus reverb signal produced by the loudspeaker array without any optimization for the playback room (non-opt (Dir+Rev)), and finally the proposed optimized signal (opt (Dir+Rev)). The direct sound scenario (Dir) and the direct sound plus reverberation scenario (Dir+Rev) were included because they are the constituent signal components used to obtain the proposed optimized rendering method, and we considered it informative to see how these scenarios gain from the optimization step. For each rendering scenario, 5 different sounds including a concert piece, a guitar, a choir and a piano and finally one human voice were used. The mean and standard errors of measurements are depicted in Figure 4. In the first-row panels, the results of subject and instrument variations for both scenario1 and scenario 2 are shown. In the second row, the results of individual instrument variations for scenario 1 and scenario 2 are respectively depicted.

According to the first-row panels, the hidden reference signals are well detected by the listeners and scored almost 100%. Because of the reverberation of the playback room, the conventional Ambisonics including all 25-SHs channels reproduced in a reverb room (Amb) leads to a high signal degradation and was judged to have a less than 40% score on the 100% scale. The beamformed direct sound (Direct) only provided the directional cues, but does not reproduce the desired spectral characteristics of the reference signal and its scoring is below the conventional Ambisonics. According to the Figures 2 and 3, the direct signal without optimization (Direct) shows more energy in low frequencies even in comparison with the conventional Ambisonics signal and this is likely the reason for low score of this signal. The non-optimized case (non-opt (Dir+Rev)) including direct sound and two of SHs ($W(t)$ and $Y(t)$ signals) shows the worst quality between all signals whereas this signal after optimization (opt (Dir+Rev)) specifically for the high-energy components in the low frequencies shows a considerable enhancement. In the optimization method, only two Ambisonics channels (W and Y) are used that in some applications can substantially reduce the required transmitted data compared to a standard higher-order Ambisonics. The individual instrument variations in both scenarios 1 and 2 show improvement in all instruments for the proposed optimization method specifically for the speech signal in which the low-frequency components are extremely degraded because of the reverberation of playback room.

Fig.4. Results of the multi-stimulus hidden reference scaling experiment over headphones. In two panels of first row, the means and the standard errors across the subjects and instruments are shown., The circles and diamonds illustrate the results for scenario 1 and scenario 2, respectively. The signals are the recording-room reference signal (Reference), a conventional Ambisonics rendering within the playback room (Amb), the uncompensated direct sound in the playback room (Direct), non-optimized direct and reverberant rendering within the playback room (non-opt (Dir+Rev)), and the proposed perceptually optimized rendering (Opt (Dir+Rev)). The panels of the second row show the results of individual instrument variations for scenario1 and scenario 2.

4.2 Evaluation based on Eigenmike Measurements

For a more practical evaluation of the proposed method, an Eigenmike microphone array [27] was used for simulating real recordings. Two recordings from a lecture room at two different distances (3m and 8m) between the loudspeaker and the microphone array we used respectively named the “near scene” and the “far scenes”. The far scene scenario is shown in Figure 5. The playback room is again simulated using the RAZR toolbox [24]. The room dimensions and positions of loudspeakers are similar to Table 2, but a higher reverberation time is simulated. The reverberation times of both recording and simulated playback room are in about 1 second.

Similar to the simulated recording room, to record the direct sound and reduce the sidelobe level in extraction of direct sound, an axis symmetric beamformer [19] with Dolph-Chebyshev weightings [20] is used. The recorded direct sound in the Eigenmike has a practical limitation that must be considered. Higher-order Ambisonics signals are restricted to increasingly limited operating

frequency range in order to limit the maximum amount of the system self-noise generated during the encoding process [6].

Fig.5. The Eigenmike recording for the far scene scenario in a lecture room.

In the lower frequencies, specifically frequencies below 400 Hz, the beampattern is wider and as a consequence there is a high amount of the reverb sound energy leaking to the direct-sound signal which may limit the ability of the proposed method to adjust the effective direct-to-reverberant energy to the desired value in the playback room. This is different from the processing of the simulated recording room that all of higher-order Ambisonics signals can be encoded in all frequencies. To evaluate the performance of the beamformer, spectrograms of omni-directional (W channel) and also the beamformer output for both far and near scenes are depicted in Figure 6.

The beamformer can attenuate the reverb sound across a large range of frequencies. But, at low frequencies, because of the wider pattern of the beamformer, there is energy leakage of the reverb signal into the beamformer. This energy can be to some extent compensated by the proposed processing procedure which will simply reduce the amount of reverberant energy injected in the playback room by the direct VBAP and both W and Y channels according to Eq (18).

The results of optimization of energy and ICs and the comparisons with the non-optimized signals for the near scene and far scene scenarios are respectively depicted in Figures 7 and 8. According to the panels A and B, the optimized reverb signal has closer energy curve to that of

the reference signal. Also, it is seen that all of Gammatone filter bank outputs in panels C and D show a near to ideal compensation of ICs, much better than the IC found for conventional Ambisonics without room compensation. In panels E and F similar to the simulated recording room, the optimized signal specifically at the low frequencies in which the reverberation is dominant has closer energy curves to that of the reference signal.

In Figure 9, the results of the multi-stimulus scaling listening test using Eigenmike recordings and simulated playback room are shown. The direct dry sound (Direct) showed poorest performance specifically in the far scene scenario. In difference to the results of simulated recording room in Figure 4, the worst scores of Eigenmike-recording in far scene scenario belong to the Direct case because of lower quality of the direct VBAP sound according to the discussion in section 5.2.1 and Figure 6. The direct sound of the near scene scenario is only scored a bit more than the non-opt (Dir+Rev) case. The problem with the far scene is because of leakage of reverberation and also lower direct to reverb ratio and also more distance between the source and microphone. Also because of the lower quality of the direct sound, the difference between scores of conventional Ambisonics (Amb) and the compensated signal (opt (Dir+Rev)) is lower than results of the simulated room (Figure 4).

Fig.6. The outputs of W channel (left panels) and beamformer (right panels) for near and far scenes. In the high frequencies, the beamformer attenuates the reverb sound, but in the frequencies below 400 Hz because of wider pattern of the beamformer, there are energy leakage of the reverb signal into the beamformer.

Fig.7. The results of optimization and comparison with the non-optimized signals for the near scene scenario. In panels A and B, the ATF of reverb sound at the output of all Gammatone filters for the reference, non-optimized and optimized signals respectively for the right and left ears of dummy head are shown. In figures C and D, the ICs for perceptually important frequencies below 1500 Hz are depicted. In panels E and F, the ATF of the reference, direct, optimized and standard Ambisonics signals of near scene scenario for the right and left ears are compared.

Fig.8. The results of optimization and comparison with the non-optimized signals for the far scene scenario. In panels A and B, the ATF of reverb sound at the output of all Gammatone filters for the reference, non-optimized and optimized signals respectively for the right and left ears of dummy head are shown. In figures C and D, the ICs for perceptually important frequencies below 1500 Hz are depicted. In panels E and F, the ATF of the reference, direct, optimized and standard Ambisonics signals of far scene scenario for the right and left ears are compared.

Fig.9. Results of the multi-stimulus hidden reference scaling experiment over headphones. In two panels of first row, the mean-score and the standard error across the subjects and instruments are shown., The circles and diamonds illustrate the results of robustness evaluation for near and far-distances scenarios, respectively. The panels of the second row show the results of individual instrument variations for the robustness evaluation of near distances scenario and the far distances scenario.

According to the instrument variations scorings in the second row of Figure. 9, there is improvement in similarity for almost all instrument in the compensated signals (opt (Dir+Rev)) in comparison to the conventional Ambisonics (Amb).

4.3 Robustness Evaluation of reproduced Eigenmike Recordings

In this section, the effect of head rotation and displacement of the listener in the playback room are investigated. The optimized parameter obtained for the Eigenmike recordings and the playback setup in section 5.2 are kept fix here and used for the reproduction setup to evaluate the robustness of the compensation method. For the near scene scenario, the effect of the head rotation is examined. Here, the playback room is simulated by 45-degree head rotation. For the far scene

scenario both the head rotation and displacement of listener are simulated in playback room. Head rotation of -45 degree and 30 cm displacement from array center according to table 2 is considered for the far scene scenario. The results of compensation are shown in Figures 10 and 11 for the near scene and far scene, respectively. In panels A and B of Figure 10, good compensations of reverb sound energy are seen for both left and right ears. This shows the robustness of the energy-based compensation against the head rotation. The comparison between panels C and D show that the IC compensation method specifically for the Gammatone filters output near to the upper limit of accepted ICs (1500 Hz) is not robust. This is mainly because of dipole pattern of Y channel that is only optimized in the positions of left and right ears of dummy head.

Fig.10. The results of optimization and comparison with the non-optimized signals for the robustness evaluation in the near scene scenario. In panels A and B, the ATF of reverb sound at the output of all Gammatone filters for the reference, non-optimized and optimized signals respectively for the right and left ears of dummy head are shown. In figures C and D, the ICs for perceptually important frequencies below 1500 Hz are depicted. In panels E and F, the ATF of the reference, direct, optimized and standard Ambisonics signals of robustness evaluation in the near scene scenario for the right and left ears are compared.

Fig.11. The results of optimization and comparison with the non-optimized signals for the robustness evaluation in the far scene scenario. In panels A and B, the ATF of reverb sound at the output of all Gammatone filters for the reference, non-optimized and optimized signals respectively for the right and left ears of dummy head are shown. In figures C and D, the ICs for perceptually important frequencies below 1500 Hz are depicted. In panels E and F, the ATF of the reference, direct, optimized and standard Ambisonics signals of robustness evaluation in the far scene scenario for the right and left ears are compared.

For higher frequencies this point-based optimization is more critical than is seen in panel D of Figure 10. Panels E and D again show the robustness of energy-based optimization and better matching to the reference signal in comparison to the direct and conventional Ambisonics signals.

For the far scene scenario in Figure 11, there is a good robustness for compensated signal in term of reverb energy according to panels A and B and also the whole energy of signal in panels E and D. Comparison between panels C and D shows again lower similarity between ICs of compensated signal and that of the reference signal specifically for gammatone filters near to 1500 Hz. Altogether, energy-based optimization is robust against head rotation and displacement whereas IC optimization for higher frequency range is not robust.

In Figure 12, the results of the multi-stimulus scaling listening test using Eigenmike recordings and simulated playback room for robustness evaluations are shown. The results of subject and instrument variations shows that the listeners in spite of missing some ICs information in frequencies near to 1500 Hz, give higher scores in similarity to the hidden reference to the compensated signal (opt (Dir+Rev)). Informal listening

suggests that the listeners, based on the accurate localization information conveyed by the direct VBAP signal in comparison to the less accurate localization rendered by the Ambisonics scenario made their judgments in preference of the proposed method. This localization information besides compensated energy of the direct and reverb sounds outperforms the ICs dissimilarity in some frequency bands

Individual instrument variations in the second row of Figure 12 show that the speech and guitar have more improvement in the similarity score in comparison to other instruments. This can be because of the fact that these two audio signals have narrower bandwidth and more dominant frequency components in lower frequencies in comparison to others. According to panels D in Figures 10 and 11, there is still a good match between ICs of compensated signal and that of the reference signal in low frequencies. This is more obvious in instrument variations of the far scene in Figure 12. For the concert piece that has the widest frequency band, the similarity scores of optimized signal (Opt (Dir+Rev)) and conventional Ambisonic signal (Amb) are closer to each other in comparison to other instruments

Fig.12. Results of the multi-stimulus hidden reference scaling experiment over headphones. In two panels of first row, the mean-score and the standard error across the subjects and instruments are shown., The circles and diamonds illustrate the results of near and far distances scenarios, respectively. The panels of the second row show the results of individual instrument variations for the near distances scenario and the far distances scenario.

5 CONCLUSION

In this study, a new recording and reproduction method based on Ambisonics and a perceptually compensation approach for the playback room was proposed. Instead of ideally reconstructing the original sound field, the directional cues, energy and spatial diffuseness of the original, recorded, sound field are reproduced. The auditory transfer function (ATF) of the direct and reverb sounds and also the interaural coherence (IC) of the original recorded sound are preserved by using a perceptually-based optimization algorithm. For the optimization, sound fields are compared between a dummy head in the recording room and another dummy head placed in the playback room at the listener positions. For optimization, the binaural room impulse responses (BRIRs) of a source in the recording room and the loudspeakers in the playback room are needed. For the evaluation of the proposed method, a recording room simulated by the SMIR toolbox [23] and also recordings of an Eigenmike microphone array in a lecture room were used. A loudspeaker array placed in a reverberant reproduction room with different head orientations and different listener positions were simulated using the RAZR toolbox [24]. This allowed to evaluate the proposed method and its robustness for different listener positions.

For optimization, the direct and reverb sounds of a source are extracted. After obtaining the direct sound by beamforming in the Ambisonics domain, the reverb sound is extracted by subtraction of spatialized direct sound from the original SH signals. For the reverb sound instead of recording and transmission of all Ambisonics coefficient, only the pressure (W signal) and one of derivatives of pressure (Y signal) are used and the modifications of reverb signal to preserve the spatial diffuseness of original sound are performed at the playback side.

Technical and quality assessments in listening tests showed that by using the proposed compensation approach, the timbre and spatial properties of the original recorded sound are preserved and there is a significant improvement in judged quality in comparison to the conventional Ambisonics without compensation. Information of two Ambisonics channels (W and Y) are sufficient to compensate the perceptual metrics and reproduce a signal matched with the recorded reference signal. From the data transmission view, the proposed method requires only 3 signals; the beamformed direct signal, and the W and Y spherical harmonic components. In comparison to the conventional 4th order Ambisonics that uses 32 channels, this represents a considerable reduction in required storage and transmission channel capacity. Also, the listening tests showed the robustness of the algorithm against head rotation and displacement of a listener from the sweet spot which is at the center of loudspeaker array.

A current limitation of this optimization method is the requirement knowledge of the impulse responses of the recording room for the optimization procedure. Another limitation is related to the handling of only one source in

each time frame. Modifications are planned to extend this optimization framework for more than one concurrent sound source following an approach similar to Goeswein et al. [28] which does not depend on estimating source direction for rendering spatial information.

6 ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

We would like to thank the Deutsche Forschungsgemeinschaft for supporting this work as part of Project C2 of the Sonderforschungsbereich 1330 Hörakustik (HAPPAA)

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